

Ethnopharmacological uses of mammalian species among the people of Bagh, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

Many species of animals are utilized both in traditional ethnopharmaceutical industries to synthesize the potential drugs worldwide. This demands urgent implementation of conservation policies. Furthermore, documentation of cultural, social, ecological and traditional knowledge on medicinal uses associated with wild and domesticated fauna is very important. In this context present research was planned to know the ethnopharmacological uses of indigenous mammalian species used by the local communities of the Bagh, Pakistan. During the research noted that 10 species of mammals used for different diseases as; Indian barking deer is used to enhance energy; Himalayan musk deer is used to cure Joint pain and used as scent. Indian wild boar fat is used to treat joint pain. Brown bear is used to treat male potential, fat for joint pain. Grey langur is used to cure joint pain; Rhesus Macaque is used to treat joint pain, TB. House Mouse is used to treat male potential, joint, back bone pain; common leopard is utilized to heal male potential, joint, back bone pain. House rat is applied to heal joint pain, treatment of cancer, joint pain, cape hare is employed to therapy of asthma and paralysis.

Keywords: Mammals, Ethnopharmacology, Bagh, Pakistan, Musk deer

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INTRODUCTION

Traditional medicines based on parts of mammals are extremely vital to human being (Alves and Rosa, 2007; Alves *et al.*, 2007; Alves *et al.*, 2009; Riaz and Altaf, 2021; Faiz *et al.*, 2022), and lot of mammalian species are traded for different purposes especially ethnopharmacological uses (Alves and Rosa, 2007; Khan *et al.*, 2020). Documentation of traditional ethnomedicinal plant and animal knowledge is important for conservation initiatives. The marketplaces where traditional medicine sellers operate are important sales points for mammalian fauna. Conservation managers and policymakers require information on native and alien wildlife and flora gained from such marketplaces. Despite the fact that numerous wild animals have been used medicinally in rural regions in the past (Waldram *et al.*, 2000; Kang *et al.*, 2003; Aikins, 2005; Smitherman *et al.*, 2005; Whiting *et al.*, 2013; Kanwal *et al.*, 2019; Afsheen *et al.*, 2020; Aslam and Faiz, 2020; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020; Abbasi, 2021),

nothing is recognized about ethnopharmacological applications in societies of uran (Alves and Rosa, 2007; Alves *et al.*, 2007; Arshad *et al.*, 2014).

Since ancient times, various body parts of fauna have been used in treatment of health of human, and such therapies are known as “zootherapy” (Khan *et al.*, 2017; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017a; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017b; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017c; Umair *et al.*, 2017; Aslam and Faiz, 2020; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020; Mughal *et al.*, 2020; Saleem *et al.*, 2021; Saeed *et al.*, 2022; Umair *et al.*, 2022). Zootherapy has a long history and a wide geographical spread. Around “15-20%” of medications are derived from animals and over “500 species” of invertebrates is utilized to treat both common and difficult illnesses in India. Fauna as healing mediators have made major contributions to treatment of health problems all over the world x. It is believed that 8.7% of the key compounds utilized in protective medications are derived from animals. Insects are key components of contemporary medications due to their “antibacterial”, “diuretic”, “anaesthetic”, “immunological”, “analgesic” and “anti-rheumatic qualities” (Oudhia, 1995; Yamakawa, 1998; Costa-Neto and Marques, 2000; Dedeke *et al.*, 2006). Chitosan, which is generated from insect exoskeletons, is used as an anticoagulant, to decrease cholesterol levels in the blood, and to heal tissues (Goodman, 1989). Anti cancer medications have been extracted from “Asian sulphur butterflies”, “Taiwanese stag beetles”, and other animals' parts of body (Kunin and Lawton, 1996; Umair *et al.*, 2022).

Lot of fauna species are being tested for medications by ethnopharmaceutical and medicinal industries e.g. “snake venom”, which inhibits “angiotensin converting enzyme”, which is dependable for the generation of “angiotensin hormone” from an inert “precursor”, causing blood vessels to constrict and blood pressure to rise. Similarly, a variety of defensive chemicals like steroids, biogenic amines, peptides and alkaloids have been found in secretions of amphibian. These chemicals have a variety of therapeutic impact, like “cardiotoxic”, “myotoxic”, and “neurotoxic” properties. Ethnomedicinal knowledge gathered from indigenous peoples contributes greatly to the identification of novel biological resources for commercial use, primarily in the pharmaceutical industry. Furthermore, the spread of current treatments is based on indigenous tribes' customary awareness. As a result, documenting of indigenous people's traditional knowledge is critical, because the creation of modern pharmaceuticals in recent years has been highly influenced by the loss of socioeconomic and cultural features of native people across the world (Fabricant and Farnsworth, 2001; Alves and Rosa, 2005; Costa-Neto, 2005).

Many species of wild animals are utilized both in traditional health care and in pharmaceutical industries to synthesize the potential drugs worldwide. This demands urgent implementation of conservation policies. Furthermore, documentation of cultural, social, ecological and traditional knowledge on medicinal uses associated with wild and domesticated fauna is very important. In this context present study was designed to gather and document the ethno-medicinal aspects of indigenous species of mammals utilized by the native society of the Bagh, Pakistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

Bagh is mountainous area and have different elevation in different places and have high vegetation (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The map of the study area.

ASSESSMENT OF ETHNO-MAMMALOLOGY STUDY

Filed survey was conducted during 2018 to 2020. Questionnaires were used to collect ethno-mammalogical data. One hundred informants including teachers, businessman, students, labors, and army were selected based on their knowledge on cultural and medicinal aspects of mammalian species. Information on local name, medicinal use and cultural significance of each species were gathered. For identification of mammalian species field book “Mammals of Pakistan” and guides were also used (Roberts, 1997).

RESULTS

Data collected from male (92) and female (8) and all are muslims. Data collected from Non-Government employer, Housewives, laborer, students and Government employers. Data collected from different people of the study area and education of people is illiterate, primary, middle, metric, F.A, B.A, M.A, and PhD (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The education of the selected people of the study area.

Table 1: Ethno-mammalogy observation of the study area.

Sr.	Common name	Scientific name	Bagh	Rera	Dhirkot	Ganga Choti
1.	Cape hare	<i>Lepus Capensis</i>	Meat is used for the treatment of Asthma	Meat is used against Paralysis	Meat is used against Paralysis	Meat is used against Paralysis

2.	House Rat	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	Bones for joint pain, treatment of cancer	Meat is used for the treatment of joint pain	Fat are used for joint pain	Fat are used for joint pain
3.	Common Leopard	<i>Panthera Pardus</i>	Fat for male potential, joint, back bone pain	Fat for male potential, joint, back bone pain	Fat for male potential, joint, back bone pain	Fat for male potential, joint, back bone pain
4.	House Mouse	<i>Mus musculus</i>	Fat are used for joint pain	Fat are used for joint pain	Fat are used for joint pain	Fat are used for joint pain
5.	Rhesus Macaque	<i>Maccaca multatta</i>	Heart is used for TB	Fat are used for joint pain	Fat are used for joint pain	Fat are used for joint pain
6.	Grey langur	<i>Semnopithecus entellus</i>	Fat are used for joint pain	Fat are used for joint pain	Fat are used for joint pain	Fat are used for joint pain
7.	Brown Bear	<i>Ursus arectus</i>	Its fat is used for male potential, fat for joint pain	Potential	Potential	Potential
8.	Indian Wild Boar	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	Fat is used to treat joint pain	Fat is used to treat joint pain	Fat is used to treat joint pain	Fat is used to treat joint pain
9.	Himalayan Musk deer	<i>Moschus Chrysogaster</i>	Joint pain,	Used in scent	Used in scent	Used in scent
10.	Indian Barking deer	<i>Mutiacus muntjak</i>	Used to Enhance energy	Used to Enhance energy	Used to Enhance energy	Used to Enhance energy

During the research noted that 10 species of mammals used for different diseases as; Indian barking deer is used to enhance energy; Himalayan musk deer is used to cure Joint pain and used as scent. Indian wild boar fat is used to treat joint pain. Brown Bear is used to treat male potential, fat for joint pain. Grey langur is used to cure joint pain; Rhesus Macaque is used to treat joint pain, TB. House mouse is utilized to cure male potential, joint, back bone pain; common leopard is used to treat male potential, joint, back bone pain. House rat is utilized to heal joint pain, treatment of cancer, joint pain, and cape hare is utilized to heal asthma and paralysis (Table 1).

DISCUSSION

During the research noted that 10 species of mammals used for different diseases. While previous record shown that milk (Aslam and Faiz, 2020), bones (Ijaz and Iftikhar, 2021), eggs (Tariq, 2020), meat (Haidar and Bashir, 2021), biles, scale,

saliva, testis, carapace, skin, blood, and urine were utilized in ethnopharmacological applications (Wilson, 2015). According to the findings of the current study, residents of the study regions utilize fat and oil to cure backache, headache, burn, rheumatic pains, cold, skin diseases, snake bite and as a sexual problems healer. These applications are similar to previous studies that fauna fats or oil can help with CNS and old ages problems (Breteler, 2000; Haag, 2003).

Lahore residents utilize goat bone broth to cure internal wounds and fractures. This demonstrates that the matrix comprises elastic protein, inorganic minerals and collagen fibers (Hall, 2011). Local groups in both areas utilize scales of “Indian pangolin” as an impotency tonic and to eradicate hook worm in Lahore only. The presence of several chemical elements may contribute to the health advantages of Pangolin scales. However, because of illicit killing and widespread usage in traditional remedies, the “Indian pangolin” is on the edge of extinction (Jia, 2013; Zhou *et al.*, 2014).

Human’s urine is utilized to cure ear pain and herpes. Urine of hyrax, sheep, dromedary, ass, cattle, goat and rhinoceros is also helpful in the therapy of throat, ear, TB, syphilis, skin infections, rashes, mouth infection, memory loss, foot diseases, fever, eyes infections, disinfection, CNS, fungal diseases, cell proliferation, dependent kinase inhibitor p21, burn, back pain, apoptosis, asthma, antifungal, anemia, and acne (Lohani, 2011a, b; Al-Yousef *et al.*, 2012; Alves *et al.*, 2012a; Alves *et al.*, 2012b; Barros *et al.*, 2012; Kim and Song, 2013, 2014; Melo *et al.*, 2014; Mohanty *et al.*, 2014; Al-Awadi and Al-Judaibi, 2015; Vijayakumar *et al.*, 2015a; Vijayakumar *et al.*, 2015b).

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